

Fiber Bundles – 8 Theory

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Abstract:

By analyzing the primordial equation of the coupling constants series, it is possible to reason for the reason to a unique, independent arrow of time that is one sided. The argument presented similar to intended base vectors from linear algebra.

Introduction

In the 8T, we are analyzing a varying manifold, which is the connected manifold with (3,1) signature. This manifold as you know has two components, the matrix M, and the flow. The manifold has been analyzed in a Variational framework, i.e. Euler Lagrange equation to yield the main equation:

$$\frac{\partial L}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial L}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1)$$

The purpose of this short essay is to describe the relationship between the base spaces, which is the Ricci flow to the total space that is the manifold matrix tensor which we are living on. The relationship between those two spaces will be described by the concept of fiber bundle. The order in which events are accruing in this framework is firstly effected by the Ricci flow space, i.e. the base space.

$$\frac{\partial L}{\partial s} \leftarrow \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \leftarrow \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \leftarrow \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} \quad (1.1)$$

We can define a fiber bundle between the Ricci flow and the Matrix tensor. Define the base space and the total space:

$$\mathcal{R} \rightarrow \text{Base space}$$

$$\mathbb{M}_T \rightarrow \text{Total Space}$$

$$\psi: \mathbb{M}_T \rightarrow \mathcal{R} \quad (1.12)$$

$$\psi^{-1}: \mathcal{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{M}_T \quad (1.13)$$

Equation (1.12) describing the projection, or the transition between the total space, matric tensor to the base space, the flow. Equation (1.13) describe the fiber, or the transition between the base space to the matric tensor. The main point is that there are two kinds of spaces, which are connected to each other by equation (1) and the idea of fiber bundle seems to be suitable for description of that relationship, given by equation (1). The description that is than suggested is that the base space, the flow, is effecting and shaping the total space. Areas of maximal energy or curvature on the base space causing the matric to accelerate outward as we mentioned many times before.

$$\frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0, \quad -\frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0$$

Arbitrary variations on the base space than vanish into matter on the matric tensor space. Net amount of flow on the base space is translated to curvature on the matric tensor space and to bosons propagation, ripples distributions across the manifold. The idea was proven by predicting the fine structure value from the primorial series:

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \tag{1.14}$$

$$F_R \# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30:128:850:9254.. \tag{1.15}$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); \quad V \geq 0 \tag{1.16}$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \quad \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); \quad P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$8 + (1): (24 + (3)) + 3: (120 + (3)) + 5: (840 + (3)) + 7 ... \tag{1.17}$$

Another point is that, there exists transformations between the base space and total space under certain conditions as mentioned in previous papers. Such transitions could be accompanied with total space, or matric tensor deformations toward the base space, the flow, and vice versa.

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)